

RESULTS OF NATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

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1
2022

USING SWOT ANALYSIS IN EDUCATION

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Аннотация В этой статье обсуждаются современные инновационные методы развития языковых навыков обучения молодого поколения иностранным языкам а также применение и важность концептуального анализа SWOT в учебном процессе.

Annotation This article discusses modern innovative methods of developing language skills in teaching foreign languages to the younger generation, as well as the application and importance of the SWOT conceptual analysis in the educational process.

The communicative approach is becoming popular, and many of teachers are experimenting with new methods and activities. Different activities, graphic organizers and innovative methods of teaching such as «Warm up», «Brainstorming», «Vienna diagram», «Jig saw», «SWOT analysis», «Case study», «Plus, minus, interesting», «Fishbone» and etc. have been widely using in the lessons. Apart from being an excellent tool to improve the language acquisition, the use of modern methods of teaching foreign languages in the classroom provides a more meaningful context for the students. All these factors lead students to become more participative and communicative members of the class group.

One of the most well known, though still receiving little use is the SWOT analysis method (Benoit, 2009), which appeared as a distinctive approach as far as in the beginning of the 20th century. SWOT analysis is a tool used for strategic planning and strategic management in organizations. It can be used effectively to build

organizational strategy and competitive strategy. In accordance with the System Approach, organizations are wholes that are in interaction with their environments and consist of various sub – systems. In this sense, an organization exists in two environments, one being in itself and the other being outside. It is a necessity to analyze these environments for strategic management practices. This process of examining the organization and its environment is termed SWOT analysis.

Basic Elements of The SWOT Analysis

- S – Strengths
 - W – Weaknesses
 - O – Opportunities
 - T – Threats
- } Internal Environment
- } External Environment

Strengths (internal, positive factors)

- Characteristics of the business or individual that give it an advantage over others in the industry
- Positive tangible and intangible attributes, internal to an organization or individuals
- Examples – abundant financial resources, well – known brand name, lower costs (raw materials or processes) , superior management talent , better marketing skills, good distribution skills, committed employees.

Weakness (internal , negative factors)

- Characteristics that place the firm or individual at a disadvantage relative to others
- Detract the organization from its ability to attain the core goal and influence its growth
- Examples – limited financial resources, very narrow product line, limited distribution, higher costs, weak market image, poor marketing skills, limited management skills, under – trained employees.

Opportunities

- Are external attractive factors that represent reasons your business is likely to prosper
- Chances to make greater profits in the environment – external attractive factors that represent the reason for an organization to exist & develop
- Examples – rapid market growth, rival firms are complacent, changing customer needs/tastes, new uses for product discovered, economic boom, government deregulation, sales decline for a substitute product

Threats (external, negative factors)

- External elements in the environment that could cause trouble for the business – external factors, beyond an organization's control
- Arise when conditions in external environment jeopardize the reliability and profitability of the organization's business
- Examples – entry of foreign competitors, introduction of new substitute products, product life cycle in decline, changing customer needs/tastes, rival firms adopt new strategies, increased government regulation, economic downturn
- To help decision makers share and compare ideas
- To bring a clearer common purpose and understanding of factors for success

- To organize the important factors linked to success and failure in the business world
- To help individual or organization to understand their strengths and weaknesses
- It promotes strategic thinking

SWOT analysis can be used for:

- business planning,
- strategic planning,
- outsourcing a service, activity or resource,
- an investment opportunity,
- a method of sales distribution,
- competitor evaluation,
- marketing,
- an investment opportunity
 - product development,
- research reports,
- etc.

However, the SWOT analysis technology was widely adopted not only in business and policy, but also in other spheres of action, in particular, in education when training students in different disciplines. The method of strategic planning is very important in the context of changes and the development all over the world. SWOT analysis method is giving structural description of any situation, and you should give the solution for the very problem. Materials and methods of SWOT for FL study should be based on realistic professional or everyday problems and situations, and designed to motivate and actively engage students. Typically students are involved in discussions on particular problems and work out solutions or recommendations through their active group work. SWOT analysis method is also excellent topic for dialogues. It is common that Strengths (Strengths), Weaknesses (Weaknesses), Opportunities (Opportunity) and Threats (Threat) are discussed and identified by the students themselves. To be successful in SWOT studies a teacher should take into consideration the level of students' language knowledge. The best choice would be using it with the student groups of intermediate or advanced level, who may have certain problems in grammar, pronunciation or vocabulary use, but for the most part are at ease with speaking the FL.

It is necessary to build the educational process so that each student receives not only knowledge, but also the pleasure from the learning process. Of course, teachers have successfully been using long-proven teaching methods of foreign languages, but in a

rapidly changing world, we must use the latest developments, endeavor to apply the traditional scheme of learning new ideas.

The modern teacher will in fact use a variety of methodologies and approaches, choosing techniques from each method that they consider effective and applying them according to the learning context and objectives. They prepare their lessons to facilitate the understanding of the new language being taught and do not rely on one specific «best method». The advantages of the teaching methods and techniques mentioned above are numerous and their employment contributes to the development of the following students’ skills and abilities: Language learning and intercultural skills. Communication skills: written, oral and non-verbal. Critical thinking skills. Reflective learning abilities. Organizational skills and professional knowledge. Collaborative learning and team-working skills. Life-long learning habits. Managerial and workplace communication skills such as holding a meeting, describing a project, solving a problem, negotiating a contract, giving a presentation, etc. All of these methods and techniques force students into real-life situations and require them to get involved into managerial and workplace communication. It should be noted that one of the main ideas of introducing these methods and techniques into FL courses is to provide opportunities for realistic learning situations, in particular to enable students to learn and use a FL in tasks related to and facilitating their study of other institute and university courses. The SWOT analysis method, case study method, language portfolio, essays and research, oral

presentations and teaching in teams are the areas of the most pronounced collaboration between a FL and other university courses as the tasks should be set in such a way to include the content covered as assignments or projects in professional courses. This not only enables the connecting of the professional knowledge and language knowledge in a meaningful way, but also promotes peer and collaborative learning in a realistic environment, which is one of the key methodological recommendations in contemporary. In a conclusion, implementing SWOT analysis method in English teaching/ learning environment will be effective.

The implementation of this very method leads students to analyze, think critically and evaluate the situation effectively. By the help of this method all four Integrated skills (listening, reading, writing, speaking) and presentation skills are developed. This method provides the formation of perfect, highly qualified specialists in the future. It is necessary to build the educational process so that each student receives not only knowledge, but also the pleasure from the learning process.

Literatures

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